

ABSTRACT

This study aimed to ascertain the school heads' interpersonal leadership skills, teachers' pedagogical competence, parents' involvement, and learners' performance. The participants of the study were the 30 randomly selected school heads and their corresponding grade 1-3 teachers and 300 randomly selected parents (10 for every school) of the grade 3 pupils who took the Language Assessment for Primary Grades (LAPG) test 2014- 2015 in the districts of Dumangas II and Barotac Nuevo. Five separate instruments were used, which included School Heads' Interpersonal Leadership Questionnaires and Parents' Involvement in School Questionnaires. Performance Appraisal System for Teachers (PAST) ratings for 2012- 2015 were also utilized. To describe and interpret the data means and standard deviations. Pearson's r set at .05 alpha level was used for inferential statistics. Study results reveal that generally, school heads' interpersonal leadership skill, as assessed by themselves and their teachers, is "greatly practiced." On the other hand, school heads' general assessment of their interpersonal skill is also "greatly practiced." Moreover, "greatly practiced" is also the entire assessment of teachers on school heads' interpersonal leadership skills and in terms of communication skills and relationship-building skills. Teachers' perceived their pedagogical competence as "very satisfactory." Generally, parents were also "highly involved" in school. As an entire group, pupils' LAPG performance is "near mastery." Generally, there is no significant relationship between the school head's interpersonal leadership skills and teachers' pedagogical competence. The same is true whether the school head or the teachers gave the rating for interpersonal leadership skills in terms of communication skills and relationship-building skills. Likewise, there is no significant relationship between the school head's interpersonal leadership skills and pupils' LAPG performance. Furthermore, a significant relationship exists between the school heads' interpersonal leadership skills and parents' involvement in (a) communication and (b) participation in school projects and programs. However, no significant relationship between school heads' interpersonal leadership skills and such categories as (c) facilitation of school learning at home and involvement in school governance. Interpersonal leadership is an essential leadership skill that each school head must possess. However, it will not significantly affect teachers' pedagogical competence and learners' performance. Parents' involvement in school is the opposite because school heads' interpersonal leadership skill relates to it.

Keywords: *School heads, interpersonal leadership skills, pedagogical competence, parental involvement, student performance*

INTRODUCTION

The key to an effective school is an effective school administrator, and the practical school administrator's role is critical to the success of any school improvement efforts (Fullan, 2001).

School heads play an essential role in school success. Palaniuk (2008) stated that the school head's leadership sets the school's tone, the teaching climate, the level of professionalism and morale of teachers, and the degree of concern for what learners may or may not become. He added that one could almost point out to the school head as the key to success if a school is a vibrant and innovative, child-centered place, has a reputation for excellence in teaching, and the learners perform well to the best of their ability.

In a school setting, as the school head sets the tone of success, there is a severe need for what is called "getting along well" with others; as the (Katz, 2009) "Three Skill Model" pointed out, "Human leadership Skill." Human skill refers to proficiency in dealing with and understanding people and using this understanding to get the best out of them individually or in groups. Nag (2011) also explained that human skill is also called interpersonal skill, which involves knowing how to react well to people. It is a kind of skill further categorized by Klein, DeRouin, and Salas (2006) into communication and relationship-building skills. As mentioned by Barrie (2005), the concept of teamwork, collaboration, and collegiality positions the school head to be effective in interpersonal skills in order to reach educational goals, and the school head's role includes that of a decision-maker that requires effective interpersonal communication (Parsons & Cable, 2001). Also, it was mentioned by Sorenson and Machell (2014) that a school head must be a builder of relationships among several constituents, including teachers, learners, parents, and the community since (Sharma, 2002) believes that their perceptions make up a dimension that considerably measures school heads' competencies.

As teachers perceive, school heads' leadership is one of the many variables affecting the

school's productivity (Scotti & William, 2015). Teachers look up to their school heads and their kind of leadership for guidance and inspiration. Effective school heads inspire confidence, loyalty, trust, and respect (National Association of Elementary School Principals, 2007). Wenglinisky (2000) emphasized that school heads' support of leader professional development effectively enhances teacher knowledge and performance.

Likewise, effective school heads are also responsible for establishing a school-wide vision of commitment to high standards and the success of all learners (Porter & McKibbin, 2008). According to Portin et al. (2003), one highly successful school head summed up his effort in this area in a somewhat succinct fashion by working hard to get to know every learner, even by name, their families, grades, test scores progress, failures, achievements and involvement in school activities and programs. As stated by Hallinger and Heck (2010), even though schools must work towards various goals, they take the position that school leadership must first and foremost be directed toward improving learners' learning.

Furthermore, the study by Lucas (2000) also emphasizes the critical role of the school head in maintaining good relationships with the children and their parents, even though teachers are the ones building these relationships. Parents' involvement has been trusted for years as a significant factor in the pupils' or students' achievement (Harris et al., 2007). William (2009) believed that being an involved, active parent can have a far-reaching impact on the child's development and the school. Constantino (2007) pointed out that the school head's belief is essential in cultivating family engagement to enhance learners' learning.

The researcher has three main reasons why this study was conducted. First, conducting this study is important because it provides new insights for improving administrative relations with teachers. Second, the kind of relationship established between the school head and teachers serves as a bridge to communicate with learners' parents since school heads do not have direct contact with them. Third, the researcher aims that the foundation of interpersonal relations of school heads will lead to the establishment of the school head, teacher, and school triad, which leads to the first and foremost goal of the school, which is to improve learners' performance. School heads and those who aspire to have an administrative position will also become aware of the importance of interpersonal leadership skills in effectively building trust, promoting respect, boosting teacher morale, improving teacher performance and parents' involvement in schools, and raising learners' academic performance. As cited by (Rieg, 2008), it should always be remembered that behind every great school stands a great school head.

Interpersonal leadership theory by (Klein et al., 2006) is an umbrella term that refers to goal-directed behaviors, including communication and relationship-building competencies. Such a term focuses on effectively communicating and getting along with others. As added by (Kambeya, 2008), this is one significant thing that school heads must cling to because they are developed through interaction with teachers and the community. Thus, this study was anchored in this theory for it provides necessary clarity for the relationship of the school heads' interpersonal leadership skills to teachers, learners, and their parents. Varied instruments used led the researcher to find existing relationships that will serve as an avenue for school heads to strengthen communication and relationship with teachers, parents, and the community.

In this study, school heads' interpersonal leadership skill was measured to determine how this relates to encouraging teachers to be effective learning channels and communication between the school and learners' performance and their parents' school involvement. It will become one way for the school head to put the teacher on his or her right track when it comes to becoming effective in his or her everyday endeavor as an educator. A better understanding of teachers' unique behaviors, intelligence, and capabilities can also be a weapon for relating to them well and having a school with a foundation of camaraderie and oneness.

As anchored on Katz's (2009) Three Skill Model, this study examined the relationship among school heads' interpersonal leadership skills, teachers' pedagogical competence, parents' involvement, and learners' performance.

METHODOLOGY

Research Design. Descriptive-correlational research was used in the study. Descriptive studies are primarily concerned with finding out what is; conditions of relationship that exist; practices that prevail; beliefs; points of view or attitudes that are held; processes that are going on; effects that are being felt, or trends that are developing. On the other hand, correlational research, as stated by Fraenkell and Wallen (2003), involves collecting data in order to determine the degree to which a relationship exists between two or more variables.

Participants/Respondents. For the final conduct of the study, the districts of Dumangas II and Barotac Nuevo were chosen, and the following methods were carried out:

First, lists of public elementary schools were obtained from the district offices of Dumangas II and Barotac Nuevo. Slovin's formula was used in determining the 30 schools for the study. Based on the recommendation (Frankel & Wallen, 2003), the minimum correlational study must be no less than 30. Through a fishbowl method, 15 schools from Dumangas II and 15 schools from Barotac Nuevo were randomly drawn, and automatically, school heads were asked and agreed to become respondents of the study, and so with the Grade 1- 3 permanent teachers of the chosen schools. In each school, the ten randomly selected parents of grade 3 learners who took the 2015 Language Assessment for Primary Grades (LAPG) were also chosen as respondents. As part of the investigation, the 2015 LAPG results of each chosen school were also obtained from the district office, and 2012- 2015 PAST ratings of each teacher respondent.

To determine their perception of their interpersonal leadership skills, the school heads or principals accomplished the personal data and the set of researcher-made questionnaires on interpersonal leadership skills in terms of communication and relationship-building skills.

On the other hand, to discover teachers' perceptions of their school heads' interpersonal leadership skills, they also completed the same set of researcher-made questionnaires on School Heads' Interpersonal Leadership Skills. The questionnaire they accomplished also focused on school heads' interpersonal leadership skills in terms of communication and relationship-building skills, while accomplishing the personal data part of the questionnaire was optional.

Lastly, parents also accomplished questionnaires on Parents' School Involvement. It included questions to find parents' perceptions of their involvement in the schooling of their child or children. They completed a questionnaire on communication, participation in school projects and programs, facilitation of school learning at home, and involvement in school governance.

Data Collection Procedure. The Schools Division Superintendent, District Supervisors, and School Heads first secured permission to conduct the study. As soon as consent was granted, the researcher personally distributed and administered copies of the data-gathering instruments among the respondents with the help of the school's district supervisors, teachers, and bookkeepers in the districts of the schools involved in the study. Three surveys The researcher ensured the confidentiality of the collected information among the respondents and assured the respondents. As suggested by Christians (2000), personal data should be secured or concealed and made public behind a shield of anonymity. In this study, informed consent was observed as it is in line with Blumberg et al. (2005) interpretation that consents to participate in research is not a straightforward matter. Patterned in Makhanu (2010), the researcher emphasized recognizing objectivity as vital during data analysis to ensure that the collected data were interpreted correctly. The investigator prepared a schedule of data gathering on selected schools. After the accomplished data-gathering instruments were retrieved, the obtained data were coded, tallied and tabulated, and computer processed for statistical analysis.

Data Analysis Procedure. The data gathered for this quantitative study were subjected to statistical software. The descriptive statistics used were means and standard deviations. Pearson's r set at a .05 alpha level of significance was employed for inferential statistics. The obtained means were used to describe the school heads' interpersonal leadership skills as a whole and in terms of communication skills and relationship-building skills (self-assessment and teacher assessment), the teachers' effectiveness based on 2014- 2015 PAST rating, parents' involvement in school and learners' performance bases on LAPG result. To determine the heterogeneity or homogeneity of the mean scores of the school heads' interpersonal leadership skills as a whole and in terms of communication skill and relationship-building skill self-assessment and teacher assessment), the teachers' pedagogical competence, parents' involvement in schools and learners' performance level in the 2015 LAPG, the standard deviation was used. To ascertain the significant relationships between the school heads' interpersonal leadership skills and teachers' pedagogical competence, between the school heads' interpersonal leadership skills and parental involvement in school, between the school heads' interpersonal leadership skills and learners' academic performance and between the principals' interpersonal leadership skills, teachers' teaching performance, parental involvement in school and learners' academic performance, the Pearson's r set at .05 alpha level was utilized.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Data in Table 1 present that both school heads and their teachers assessed interpersonal leadership skills as "greatly practiced," school heads' self-assessment (M= 3.67, SD= 0.25), and

teachers' assessment of their school Theirnal leadership skill ($M= 3.68$, $SD= 0.33$). In general, their interpersonal leadership skill was "greatly practiced" ($M= 3.68$, $SD= 0.23$). In terms of Communication Skills, data also reveals it as "greatly practiced" ($M= 3.67$, $SD= 0.23$), and so Relationship- Building Skills were also "greatly practiced" ($M= 3.68$, $SD= .23$). The standard deviations ranging from 0.23 to 0.34 showed a narrow dispersion from the overall mean. This indicates that both school heads' and teachers have homogeneity in their perception of school heads' interpersonal leadership skills.

Table 1. School Heads' Interpersonal Leadership Skill

Category	Mean	Description	SD
1. Self-Assessment (General)	3.67	greatly practiced	0.25
A. School Heads' Interpersonal Leadership Skill- Communication	3.65	greatly practiced	0.26
B. School Heads' Interpersonal Leadership Skill (Relationship-Building)	3.68	greatly practiced	0.25
2. Teachers' Assessment (General)	3.68	greatly practiced	0.33
A. School Heads' Interpersonal Leadership Skill- Communication	3.68	greatly practiced	0.34
B. School Heads' Interpersonal Leadership Skill (Relationship-Building)	3.68	greatly practiced	0.32
3. Interpersonal Leadership Skill- Communication Skills (General)	3.67	greatly practiced	0.23
4. Interpersonal Leadership Skill- Relationship-Building Skills (General)	3.68	greatly practiced	0.23
Average	3.68	greatly practiced	0.23

Teachers' pedagogical competence, as reflected in their Performance Appraisal System for Teachers (PAST) for three consecutive years from 2012- 2015, was "very satisfactory" ($M= 8.33$, $SD = 0.20$). Regarding the PAST, overall rating description as embodied in RA 9155, a rating of 6.60- 8.59 is very satisfactory, which means that a teacher or master teacher often exceeds expectations in most areas but is not consistent. He or she displays high performance-related skills, abilities, initiatives, and productivity, exceeding requirements in many areas.

The data in Table 2 reveal that as an entire group, parent respondents' extent of involvement in school was "highly involved" ($M=3.16$, $SD=0.22$). Likewise, it is also "highly involved" in terms of communication ($M=3.19$, $SD=0.26$); participation in school projects and programs ($M=3.11$, $SD=0.32$); facilitation of school learning at home ($M=3.24$, $SD=0.19$); and involvement in school governance, ($M=3.08$, $SD=0.40$). School learning at home was facilitated first, followed by communication second, participation in school projects third, and involvement in school governance last.

Table 2. Parents' Involvement in School

Category	Mean	Description	SD
A. Communication	3.19	highly involved	0.26
B. Participation in School Projects and Programs	3.11	highly involved	0.32
C. Facilitation of School Learning At Home	3.24	highly involved	0.19
D. School Governance	3.08	highly involved	0.40
Average	3.16	highly involved	0.22

Over, all mean results of learners' Language Assessment for Primary Grades 2015 fall under "near mastery" ($M= 58.59$, $SD= 11.37$). The standard deviation is high, considering a big gap regarding the means of the school with the lowest rating ($M=39.58$) and the school with the highest rating ($M= 88.42$).

According to DepEd's viewpoint, the results of this LAPG as one of the standardized tests are improving the Department of Education in its efforts toward providing improvement of the quality of education in public schools and to provide appropriate intervention for the learners.

The significance of the relationships between the school heads' interpersonal leadership skills towards teachers' pedagogical competence, parents' involvement in school, and learners' performance was determined using Pearson's r , set at 0.05 alpha.

Three hypotheses were tested in this investigation. All three were tested using correlational relationships among school heads' interpersonal leadership skills with teachers' pedagogical competence, parents' involvement, and learners' performance.

To determine whether there are significant relationships between school heads' interpersonal leadership skills and teacher pedagogical competence, learners' LAPG performance, and parents' school involvement, the researcher used Pearson's r . Results are shown in Table 6.

Generally, there is no significant relationship between the school head's interpersonal leadership skills and teachers' pedagogical competence ($r = .26, p = .17$). School heads' interpersonal leadership does not have bearing with teachers' quest to be competent enough in teaching. Their professional and personal characteristics and punctuality have been a great factor for them to attain a "very satisfactory" or "outstanding" rating. Such a label directly reflects their pedagogical competence but has yet to exhibit a significant relationship to their school heads' interpersonal leadership skills. The same is true with school heads' assessment of their interpersonal leadership skill ($r = .09, p = .64$) and the teachers' assessment ($r = .29, p = .12$). It simply shows how the school heads perceive themselves somewhat the same with their teachers' perception with it.

Table 6 also shows results in determining the correlation between the school heads' interpersonal leadership skills and parents' involvement in general and in terms of (a) communication, (b) participation in school projects and programs, (c) facilitation of school learning at home, and (d) involvement in school governance. It shows that there is a significant relationship between school heads' interpersonal leadership skills and parents' involvement in terms of (a) communication ($r = 0.366, p = 0.047$) and (b) participation in school projects and programs, ($r = 0.436, p = 0.016$). The significance does not exhibit a total relationship. However, it shows that school heads' interpersonal leadership is something that parents consider in their response regarding communication and participation in school projects and programs. Truly, school heads' interpersonal relationship projects encourage them to take part in school. It appears that by attending PTA meetings, the desire to be informed and to be clarified with instructions by the school is innate to them. It is also the same with finding time to talk with teachers to track their children's performance and behavior and giving importance to letting the school know their appreciation for giving timely information about their children. Their interest in school affairs is also commendable. They show interest in improving school facilities through donations in cash, kind, or services. They also support the schools' holding of some worthwhile activities by openly supporting the effort of the school as well as its fundraising activities for different projects.

On the other hand, there are no significant differences between school heads' interpersonal leadership skills and parents' involvement in (c) facilitation of school learning at home ($r = 0.231, p = 0.220$), and (d) school governance, ($r = 0.346, p = 0.061$). It appears that school heads' interpersonal leadership is separate from parents' knowledge of the importance of their effort in offering their children help whenever doing homework, checking their children's notebooks, and helping their children solve academic, emotional, and social problems in school. School heads' may have commendable interpersonal leadership, but it does not also show a significant relationship with parents' involvement and awareness of existing policies, guidelines, school rules, and regulations. PTA meetings and school general assemblies enable them to make suggestions for improving the school's educational program, and their willingness to be part or officer of the PTA are backbones behind.

Generally, there is a significant relationship between the school heads' interpersonal leadership skills and parents' involvement in general ($r = 0.463, p = .010$). It shows that the kind of communication and relationship bestowed by the school head does relate to the parents' extent of involvement in school. School heads' interpersonal leadership relates enough with parents' clarity of their responsibilities and kind of involvement in their children's schooling.

Lastly, regarding school heads' interpersonal leadership skills and learners' LAPG performance, data in Table 6 reveal no significant relationship between school heads' interpersonal leadership skills and learners' LAPG performance ($r = 0.013, p = 0.948$). No matter how commendable school heads' interpersonal leadership is, it does not relate to learners' LAPG rating. School heads' themselves have little direct contact with learners, much more in such a way of their learning. However, (Mackey, 2006) points out that school heads are very important in teachers' and learners' success. He further explains that the school head influences the learning environment by articulating the vision and mission of the school. Therefore, it is in the school head's hands lies the

power to inspire, guide, and establish a good communication channel to lead the school and the Department of Education as a whole toward one common goal of attaining a learner-centered environment.

Learners' performance is not significantly related to school heads' interpersonal leadership skills. Still, it is a responsibility that needs to be done cooperatively by the whole school system, the school head, teachers, and learners' parents.

Table 3. Relationship Between School Heads' Interpersonal Leadership Skills and Teachers' Pedagogical Competence, Learners' LAPG Performance and Parents' School Involvement

Category	School Heads' Interpersonal Leadership Skill					
	School Head		Teacher		General	
	<i>r</i>	<i>p</i>	<i>r</i>	<i>p</i>	<i>r</i>	<i>p</i>
1. Teachers' Pedagogical Competence	0.09	0.64	0.29	0.12	0.26	0.17
2. Learners' Language Assessment for Primary Grades Performance					0.013	0.948
3. Parents' School Involvement (General)					0.463*	0.010
a. Communication					0.366*	0.047
b. Participation in School Projects and Programs					0.436*	0.016
c. Facilitation of School Learning at Home					0.231	0.220
d. School Governance					0.346	0.061

CONCLUSION

The school heads in 30 randomly selected schools in Dumangas II and Barotac Nuevo may be commended for a "greatly practiced" interpersonal leadership skill as perceived by themselves and their teachers as a whole and in terms of communication skills and relationship-building skills. Most school heads have bestowed good communication channels towards their teachers, whether active listening, verbal, written, assertive, or non-verbal. On the other hand, the school heads' well-established good relationship between and among teachers is also considered as a manifestation as it is measured through cooperation and coordination, intercultural sensitivity, service orientation, empathy, self-presentation, social influence, conflict resolution, and negotiation. Going back to Hoyle and Crenshaw's (2009) suggestion, school leaders must reaffirm the value of the people in the organization, whether through their commendable communication or relationship-building skill.

Teachers' pedagogical competence, as reflected in the PAST 2012- 2015 in general, reveals that most teachers got ratings that fall under the "very satisfactory" interpretation. It has little relationship with school heads' interpersonal leadership skills. It is attributed to their total awareness of their professional duties, responsibilities, and goals. Community demand and involvement and going with the latest trend in the education system are such manifestations that could have contributory factors to these teachers' overall PAST rating.

The Performance Appraisal System for Teachers, as it points to the essentials of high-quality teaching, also improves learner outcomes and reduces student achievement gaps. As stated under DepEd Memorandum No. 306 (s. 2009), PAST provides teachers with meaningful appraisals that encourage professional learning and growth. Moreover, this process is designed to foster teacher development and identify opportunities for additional support where required and thus help teachers achieve their full potential of achieving high levels of learner performance.

Parents are "highly involved" in school. This is manifested through well-established communication between school and parents, active participation in school projects and programs, well-facilitated school learning at home, and a chance to participate in school governance.

Furthermore, being in the school governance has been a challenge for school heads, teachers, and parents. Relying on section 1 of Republic Act 9155, the School Governing Council, which includes parents, teachers, learners, and community stakeholders, must continually work together to improve learners' outcomes. As a whole, the School Governing Council provides an opportunity to develop a partnership between the school, parents, and the community and improve learning performance. It

promotes the holistic development of all learners. Section 2 of Republic Act 9155 or the Governance of Basic Education Act of 2001, a holistic program known as "Education for All 2015," states that schools shall continue to harness local resources and facilitate the involvement of every community sector in the school improvement process. It emphasizes that the stakeholders of every school (school head, teachers, parents, learners, community leaders, and other groups interested in school practices) shall be able to use processes and results to determine and implement school programs to ensure continuous improvement in school quality.

"Near mastery" rating interpretation of learners' performance may be attributed to untimely implementation the K to 12 program. The goals and objectives were mandated under Department of Education Order No. 31, s—2012, which focuses on implementing the K to 12 program starting in kindergarten last June 2011. The adjustment of teachers to be the front liners in the implementation was questionable, much more so that there are minimal resources and references to be used by teachers and learners.

School heads' interpersonal leadership skills and teachers' pedagogical competence have no significant relationship. The following factors can be considered as the personal quest of teachers to grow professionally, teachers' awareness of their responsibility, and personal characteristics of relating well with learners, parents, and the community.

A significant relationship between school heads' interpersonal leadership skills is limited to parents' communication and participation in school projects and programs. Such can be attributed to parents' natural support and involvement in their child or children's education, whether at school or home. However, the other two factors, such as; facilitation of school learning at home and involvement in school governance, show little relationship with school heads' interpersonal leadership skills. Some parents are both working and have limited time to help their child or children with their homework or projects. One reason is also due to parents' educational background that they find it difficult to follow-up with their child or children with their learning tasks. Regarding involvement in school governance, hesitation is the number one factor. The idea of being rejected more than accepted is still within, even with the presence of encouragement on the part of the school.

Moreover, school heads' interpersonal leadership skill does not also relate to learners' performance. The "near mastery" description of learners' performance may not be anchored directly to the manner of school heads' communication and relationship-building skills much more that school heads' do not have direct contact with learners.

REFERENCES

- Cable, D. M., & Parsons, C. K. (2001). Socialization tactics and person-organization fit. *Personnel Psychology, 54*(1), 1-23.
- Christians, C. G. (2005). In qualitative research. *Sage Handb. Qualitat. Res*, pp. 139, 139–164.
- Constantino, S. M. (2007). Keeping parents involved through high school. *The Education Digest, 73*(1), 57.
- Fraenkel, J. R., Wallen, N. E., & Hyun, H. H. (2003). How to design and evaluate education research,(5. Baskı) New York.
- Fullan, M. (2007). *Leading in a culture of change*. John Wiley & Sons.
- Hallinger, P., & Heck, R. H. (2010). Collaborative leadership and school improvement: Understanding the impact on school capacity and student learning. *School leadership and management, 30*(2), 95-110.
- Harris, K. J., Kacmar, K. M., Zivnuska, S., & Shaw, J. D. (2007). The impact of political skill on impression management effectiveness. *Journal of Applied Psychology, 92*(1), 278.
- Kambeya, N. V. (2008). Georgia teachers' perceptions of principals' interpersonal communication skills as they relate to teacher performance.
- Katz, R. L. (2009). *Skills of an effective administrator*. Harvard Business Review Press.

- Klein, C., DeRouin, R. E., & Salas, E. (2006). Uncovering workplace interpersonal skills: A review, framework, and research agenda. *International review of industrial and organizational psychology* 2006, 21, 79-126.
- Lucas, T. (2000). The nine-year conversation. P. Senge (Ed.), *Schools that learn: A fifth discipline handbook for educators, parents, and everyone who cares about education* (pp. 289–303).
- Mackey, A. (2006). Feedback, noticing, and instruction in second language learning. *Applied linguistics*, 27(3), 405–430.
- Porter, A. C., Murphy, J., Goldring, E. B., Elliott, S. N., Polikoff, M. S., & May, H. (2006). Vanderbilt assessment of leadership in education. *The Elementary School Journal*.
- Portin, B., Schneider, P., DeArmond, M., & Gundlach, L. (2003). Making sense of leading schools: A study of the school principalship.
- Scotti Jr, W. H. (1987). ANALYSIS OF ORGANIZATIONAL INCONGRUITY USING TEACHER PERCEPTION OF THE PRINCIPAL'S LEADERSHIP BEHAVIOR. *Education*, 108(1).
- Sharma, S. (2011). Attributes of school principals-leadership qualities & capacities.

Declaration of Conflicting Interest. There are no conflicts concerning this research paper, authorship, and publication.

Funding. No funding from external sources, such as donations or grants, was received for conducting research, authorship, and publication of this paper.